

Sustaining Relationships Between People and Things

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Abstract

Fully functional products flood the world's landfill sites. Colonies of outcast objects (including toasters that still toast and microwaves that still microwave) find their way into these *underground clubs* for unwanted objects. Waste of this nature proliferates the developed world, and may be understood as a *symptom* of a failed subject object relationship. This research paper argues that the deep origins of the ecological crisis we face are firmly situated within one simple yet profoundly universal inconsistency – the emotional demands of users constantly evolve, whilst the products assigned to satisfy those demands remain comparatively frozen in time. The mountains of waste generated by this single anomaly are apocalyptic, and come at a steadily rising cost to legislation-burdened manufacturers, and perhaps more crucially, the Natural World.

Keywords: Attachment, relationship, emotionally durable design, product life, sustainability

Defining the self

Ask a developed world human to stop consuming and you might as well ask a vampire not to suck blood (Chapman, 2005 a). Consumption is not just a way of life, it is life, providing an invaluable vehicle for the ever evolving self to process and interact within a world that is both unstable, and ever changing. Searles describes the consumer's existential journey as an, unceasing struggle to differentiate himself increasingly fully, not only from his human, but also from his nonhuman environment (Searles, 1960). The drive to consume is natural, and may be described as *symptomatic* of a characteristically stimulus-hungry species existing within an over-streamlined world in which the experience of everyday life comes with the problems already solved, and the decisions already made. In these scenarios, corporate futurologists force-feed us a 'happy-ever-after' portrayal of life where technology is the solution to every problem. There is no room for doubt or complexity in their techno-utopian visions. Everyone is a stereotype, and social and cultural roles remain unchanged (Dunne et al, 2001).

The individualistic process of consumption is motivated by complex emotional drivers, and is about far more than just the purchasing of new and shinier things (Chapman, 2005 a); it is an existential journey towards the ideal or *desired* self, that through cyclic loops of desire and disappointment, becomes a seemingly endless process of serial destruction. Material artefacts are indicative of an individual's aspirations, and serve to outline their desired life direction. At the most superficial level, an object can be seen by the user to resonate with and be symbolic of the self. Thus, perceiving oneself as rich and powerful might lead to conspicuous consumption, such as owning a luxurious car or wearing designer apparel. Whereas, at a more profound psychodynamic level, having and utilizing an object can compensate for an unconsciously felt inadequacy (Cupchik, 1999).

Manufactured products serve to illustrate our individual aspirations whilst also defining us existentially; products are not merely functional, but provide important signals in human relationships (Douglas et al, 1979). Similarly, the human being is engaged, throughout his life span, in an unceasing struggle to differentiate himself increasingly fully, not only from his human, but also from his nonhuman environment (Searles, 1960). As such, possessions are used as symbols of what we are, what we have been, and what we are attempting to become (Schultz

et al, 1989), whilst providing an archaic means of possession by enabling the consumer to *incorporate* (Fromm, 1979) the meaning of a given object – in other words, the material you possess signifies the destiny you chase. As a result of this, consumers are drawn to objects in possession of that which they subconsciously yearn to become. In addition, users do not always associate meaning directly with the objects themselves, and often experience it as a result of the services that they render. For example products that support self-expression and social interaction such as cellular phones may become meaningful to the owner because of the saved messages or names and contact information of the loved ones (Jääskö et al, 2003 a).

To have seen through and therefore know is to deflower the entity (Sartre, 1969). The uptake of products is largely motivated by this notion; we consume the unknown in order to demystify and make it familiar. Waste therefore appears to be as much a part of the consumption experience as are purchase and use – it is evolution made tangible. French librarian and writer, Georges Bataille reinforces this notion through stating the general movement of exudation of waste of living matter impels him, and he cannot stop it; moreover, being at the summit, his sovereignty in the living world identifies him with this movement; it destines him, in a privileged way, to that glorious operation, to useless consumption (Botting et al, 1997). Consuming has ambiguous qualities: it relieves anxiety, because what one has cannot be taken away; but it also requires one to consume ever more, because previous consumption soon loses its satisfactory character (Fromm, 1979).

Conventional reality consists of a deeply abstracted culture of signs, or *simulations*, (Baudrillard, 1993) which motivate consumers more than the physical products themselves. This *self-actualizing* (Thompson, 2005) mode of subject object relations provides a mirror that mediates momentary reflections of individual existence. However, the continual evolution of the self-actualizing user poses a significant challenge to old or outmoded possessions that are no longer representative of the now self; transient and unstable cycles of consumption and waste are born. Studies by Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981), Schultz, Kleine and Kernan (1989), Wallendorf and Arnould (1988), Ball and Tasaki (1992) and Dittmar (1992) are conclusive in their relating of attachment behaviours toward individualistic concepts of self.

In a paper entitled 'Meaningful product relationships', Batterbee and Mattelmaki describe a survey where stories are collected about possessions with which users have meaningful associations. Their proposition is that meanings, experiences and meaningful relationships with products are developed over a time span and they are often related to life situations (Batterbee et al, 2004). From this research, 3 categories of objects were defined, that facilitate the understanding of different kinds of subject object attachment; these categories are; *Meaningful Tool* where the activity an objects enables, rather than the object itself, is the thing of meaning; *Meaningful Association*, in which a product is considered significant as it carries cultural and/or individual meaning and *Living Object* (Jordan, 2000) wherein an emotional bond is created between an individual and a product. Indeed, issues of design and meaning are highly complex, and more tacit and hidden aspects such as *product meaning* or *personal motivation* have influence in the user experience but are not that easily recognized or communicated to design, or even directly affected by design (Jääskö et al, 2003 b).

Though it may be possible to design objects that elicit broadly authored emotional responses, the specific character of response is largely beyond designers' capabilities due to idiosyncrasies of each individual user. In this way, designers cannot craft an experience per se, but only the conditions or *levers* that might create an intended experience (Forlizzi et al, 2000). What those required conditions are however, is still unclear to design. People can differentially attend to the sensory qualities of the design object and attach diverse personal meanings onto it because they see it used in various contexts. Their reactive emotions will therefore reflect personal associations and meanings, which are projected onto the object (Cupchik, 1999). Therefore, recognizing that users consider products as part of themselves is key to understanding the meaning of objects (Belk, 1988).

Until the middle of the 20th century consumer durables were generally viewed as investments and, within reasonable cost boundaries, were designed to last as long as possible. Since then, however, planned obsolescence, the deliberate curtailment of a product's life span, has become commonplace, driven by, for example, a need for cost reductions in order to meet 'price points', the convenience of disposability, and the appeal of fashion (Cooper, 2004). We are currently experiencing a societal shift that is steering us away from deep communal values toward a

contemporary mode of individuality fragmented over countless relationships with objects and the experiences they mediate. This has cast us in an abstract version of reality in which relationships are sought from toasters, mobile phones and other fabricated experiences. During recent years, there has been a move away from interpersonal relationships toward a newer and faster mode of relations (Brunner, 1996). Today, empathy is encountered not so much with each other but through fleeting embraces with manufactured, and evermore technologically advanced artefacts. Indeed, we do amazing things with technology, and we're filling the world with amazing systems and devices, but we find it hard to explain what this new stuff is for, or what value it adds to our lives. When it comes to innovation, we are looking down the wrong end of the telescope: away from people, toward technology. Industry suffers from a kind of global autism (Thackara, 2001). The Design Transformation Group argue that a proposed shift, away from immateriality and anonymous experience towards reflexive encounters, is seemingly only the crest of a larger cultural wave which is rapidly imparting greater understanding into the way we perceive, condition and create the world in which we live (de Groot, 1997).

Sustainable design is symptom-focussed

Despite growth as a specialist approach to design, sustainable design remains unresolved (Treanor, 2005). Furthermore, the word *sustainable* has been slapped onto everything from sustainable forestry to sustainable agriculture, sustainable economic growth, sustainable development, sustainable communities and sustainable energy production. The widespread use of the term indicates that many people conclude that the dominant, industrial models of production are unsustainable (Duvall, 2004). However, through this overuse, the impact of a well-intentioned term has been weakened.

Amidst the frantic scramble to comply with forthcoming environmental legislation, such as the European Union Directive on Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), the underlying drivers to the environmental crisis we currently face are overlooked. The WEEE directive calls on members of the EU to implement the legal framework to ensure that producers take responsibility for their electric and electronic products at end of life – representing the fastest growing waste sector in the EU, WEEE is a significant piece of legislation – particularly so, in

the context of product longevity (Chapman, 2006). During the last decade alone, consumption of household goods and services in the UK has risen by 67%, and household energy consumption by 7% - consumption is not only growing in magnitude, but the throughput of manufactured goods is speeding up. The pattern of consumption with many types of consumer goods is shortening functional lives as goods are predestined as waste (Ginn, 2004).

As Europe's leading household appliance manufacturer, Bosch Siemens in 2004 forecasted annual costs running to some 60-million euros (BSH Bosch, 2004), just to remain in compliance with the forthcoming legislative demands of the WEEE Directive (Chapman, 2006). According to Uwe Hennack, CEO of Bosch Siemens Home Appliances Ltd., the challenge is to design products that last longer, are lower cost to recycle, affordable to the consumer, use less waste energy and are produced in an environment that is environmentally friendly (BSH Bosch, 2004). Though it is not always easy for consumers to identify products designed for long life spans (Christer et al, 2004).

The threat of litigation for non-compliance will force many to re-appraise their product portfolios. As a consequence, such legislative instruments might establish frameworks and drivers for a more formalised design response to unsustainable consumption (Park, 2004). Today however, products designed for take-back are still geared toward disassembly and recycling and/or reuse. This is because eco-design usually functions at an operational level and is unlikely to hold much potential for radical change because it works within the same thinking that caused the problems in the first place (Lofthouse, 2004).

Today, sustainable design is predominately characterised by strategic approaches such as recycling, the specification of biodegradable materials and design for disassembly, all of which attend to the symptoms of what is in essence a fundamentally flawed system; as such, the inefficient consumer machine persists and consumers continue avidly to consume only now they do so with recycled materials instead of virgin ones (Chapman, 2005 a). Indeed, passive consumer attitudes to the ecological crisis we face are enforced further by the misguided preconception that comfort must be sacrificed in order to make positive change – the changes in living that would be required are believed to be so drastic that people prefer the future

catastrophe to the sacrifice they would have to make now (Fromm, 1979). Warped notions of ascetic lifestyles abounding with non-enjoyment invade the consumer psyche, rendering the prospect of a greener existence an undesirable alternative.

We lead a resource hungry existence, taking out a great deal more from the Earth than we put back. Even bearing in mind a very loose definition of development, the anthropocentric bias of the statement springs to mind; it is not the preservation of nature's dignity, which is on the international agenda, but to extend human-centred utilitarianism to posterity (Sessions, 1995). Resources - as we like to call matter that we have a commercial use for - are being transformed at a speed far beyond the natural self-renewing rate of the biosphere. Consequently, reserves of useful matter are running low and many will soon have vanished. The human race was fortunate enough to inherit a 3.8 billion-year old reserve of natural capital (Hawken et al, 1999). At present rates of consumption it is unlikely that there will be much of it left by the end of this century. In addition, since the mid-eighteenth century more of nature has been destroyed than in all prior history (Hawken et al, 1999) – in the past fifty years alone the human race has stripped the world of a fourth of its topsoil and a third of its forest cover. In total one third of all the planets resources have been consumed within the past four decades (Burnie, 1999).

The colossal throughput of materials and energy that has become so characteristic of modern life is a contemporary legacy, emerging from the shortsighted merging of excessive material durability with short-lived product use careers, or *career plans* (van Hinte, 1997). In failing to address the emotional drivers that fuel the uptake and discarding of material artefacts, sustainable design resigns itself to a peripheral endeavour, rather than pioneering positive social, economic and environmental reformation, as it potentially could (Chapman, 2005 a). It therefore must be said that in their current guise, sustainable design methodologies lack genuine depth – recyclable 'waste', biodegradable 'waste', disassemble-able 'waste' etc. – and as such, adopt a symptom-focussed approach comparable in ethos to Western Medicine; in consequence, deeper strategic possibilities are overlooked (Chapman, 2006). Feel good after measures such as recycling bare grave similarity to someone who quits smoking on his deathbed (Palahniuk, 1999). Increased recycling does not reduce the flow of material and energy through the economy but it does reduce resource depletion and waste volumes (Stahel, 1986).

Sustainable design methodologies seldom engage with the more fundamental questions such as the *meaning* and *place* of products in our lives, and the contribution of materials goods to what might be broadly termed *the human endeavour* (Walker, 2006). In consequence, the consumer machine continues to rage forth practically unchanged, leaving designers to attend the periphery, healing mere symptoms of what is, in essence, a fundamentally flawed system.

Relationships between people and things

Though strategic approaches to product life extension are fairly commonplace, in most instances, durability is characterized simply by specifying resilient materials, repairable technologies and the application of advanced design engineering methodologies that reduce the likelihood of blown circuits, stress fractures and other physical failures; engineers therefore celebrate in triumph as fully functioning vacuum cleaners emerge from a five-year landfill hiatus. It must be questioned as to whether this is durable product design, or simply the designing of durable waste? (Chapman, 2005 b) Once emotional attachments weaken and these products are eventually discarded, this *objective* model of durability has a particularly destructive impact on the biosphere. Therefore, designing *physical durability* into products is pointless, if users lack the desire to keep them. Indeed, a great deal of debate surrounds the need for an increase in the *emotional durability* of products; strategies to enable this *need* are less forthcoming, though several approaches are important to note.

For instance, van Hinte urges that precision and control are oftentimes the precursors of detachment behaviours; the ideology of *fuzzy interactions* with objects runs contrary to the prevailing model of popular design, with its focus on idiot-proof interfaces; in many cases, imperfections can be endearing and help to create a bond with the user. Van Hinte's research also explores design strategies for desirable ageing; ageing is inevitable, and we need to begin to design 'with' it, rather than 'against' it to enable products to *age with dignity* (van Hinte, 1997). Similarly, Park explores the potential for what he calls 'piggybacking' – the creation of new *bolt-on* products that attach to technologically obsolete products to bring them back into service. This is a particularly challenging idea, as it deals with the complex issue of *technological*

obsolescence head-on. This is quite different to *relative obsolescence* where both psychological and social aspects of consumer behavior become evident through the migration of interest toward newer objects with greater social and cultural currency, often regardless of advancements in technology.

Slowing the onset of ageing in this way, and sustaining an object's currency with the user represents an important direction in product life research; note that *slow design* is 'slow' not 'static', as Alastair Fuad Luke, vice president of SlowLab reminds us. Our existence has no foundation on which to rest except the transient present. Thus, its form is essentially unceasing motion, without any possibility of that repose which we continually strive after (Schopenhauer, 1970). Furthermore, because everything moves so fast, and we cannot stop it, we have to create some *islands of slowness*. Design, in all its history, but especially in more recent years, has been an agent of acceleration. Is it possible to conceive of solutions combining real-time interactions with the possibility of taking time for thinking and contemplation? (Manzini, 2002) Current consumption operates within a linear production-consumption system that takes resources, makes them into products, then discards or wastes them – slowing consumption offers a direct response to unsustainable consumption. By slowing the mass flows in the linear production-consumption economy a level of sustainability could be achieved (Park, 2004). Yet it must also be noted that such consumption beyond minimal and basic needs is not necessarily an unnatural, or a *bad* thing in and of itself, as throughout history we have always sought to find ways to make our lives a bit easier to live (Shah, 2003).

Dunne and Raby argue that both the scope and intensity of emotional experiences delivered via contemporary products are incredibly limited, and offer very little to users – even though industrial design plays a part in the design of extreme pain (e.g. weapons) and pleasure (e.g. sex aids), the range of emotions offered through most electronic products is pathetically narrow (Dunne et al, 2001). As such, interacting with this technocratic and de-personalized environment fuels a reactionary mind set that hankers after meaningful content, mystery and emotion (de Groot, 1997). Industrial design has become a subordinate packager of technology – housing hardware within intelligible skins that enable thoughtless, and effortless, subject object interaction. Indeed, the computational and communicative devices that now assist almost every

transaction in our daily lives are designed as dull and servile boxes that respond to our commands in a state of neutrality; stress and techno-phobia are the result (de Groot, 2002).

Van Nes develops strategies that aim to induce a behavioral response within the user through the scripting of *narrative experiences* within products, which unfold like stories, through use. This is believed to be an effective strategy that enables objects to always offer the user with something new, something different. Without consideration to narrative experience, most consumer products are like stories with an incredible opening line, but which just continue repeating it throughout. Their narrative capabilities are pathetically limited, and in these superficial scenarios, predictability – like rot – promptly sets in to forge colossal voids between the subject and the object (Chapman, 2005 a, p120).

Sonneveld and Bonekam are developing research into the ageing of plastics, and perhaps more interestingly, the way we perceive and interpret this narrative process as users. They argue that unlike traditional materials like wood, steel and stone, plastics are not perceived as a clear category with predictable properties, but rather as the fuzzy products of New Alchemy, where anything can happen ... consumer experience is categorized by an ambiguous attitude towards plastic (Sonneveld et al, 2004). If enduring relationships between emotionally demanding users and comparably inert products are to be nurtured, we as designers must consider deeper sensorial dimensions of objects. This is not to say that everything should be made using wood, denim or, perhaps, leather; instead, provocative design concepts could emerge that challenge our social desire for a scratch-free world, illustrating how the onset of ageing could concentrate rather than dilute the gestalt. Natural materials dominate discussions regarding the ageing process. This is problematic, given that electronic products almost exclusively utilize synthetic polymers. Most of us are familiar with the manner of *desirable ageing* found in narrative rich products such as denim jeans.

Purchased like blank canvases, jeans are worked on, sculpted and personified over time. The character they acquire provides reflection of one's own experiences, taking the relationship beyond user and used to creator and creature. Similar in philosophy to the way in which voice recognition software sculpts itself around the phonic idiosyncrasies peculiar to a particular user,

jeans become tailored to the physical individualities of the wearer to become a part of them (Chapman, 2005 a, p116). You have a close relationship with your jeans. Your jeans are a second skin, faded and shaped and ripped and bulged by your experiences. They are lived in. After a party they smell like a party. When ageing is embraced in this way, we can see that the transformative nuance of decay can be utilized by designers to great effect, ensuring that products are free to age and evolve gently through the course of time, rather than falling ruthlessly out of favour the moment their glossy façades of newness begin to peel away (Chapman, 2005 a, p130).

Emotionally durable objects such as jeans dodge the *deflowering gaze* (Sartre, 1969) of waste by possessing meaning(s), that grow with the user, to ensure that the subject and the object co-evolve, rather than the one-sided development that usually takes place where the user outgrows the static product in a handful of weeks or even days. What can be understood from these success stories, and how can this inform the design of more *emotionally durable* products? After all, what people basically want is a well functioning and up to date product that meets their altering needs. The dynamic nature of this desire requires a similar approach: the development of dynamic and flexible products (van Nes et al, 2005).

De Groot's work on consciousness and alterity is also of great significance here. Alterity is experienced by users as the feeling that something is both autonomous and is in possession of its own free will; when objects embody this eccentric quality, the relationships forged between subject and object are frequently strong and long lasting. According to Hybs, alterity relations are the dimension of an interaction in which the object of one's intention is perceived in terms of otherness. This particularly elusive concept could be described as the felt sensation of the interaction with an autonomous or intelligent object, animal or individual (Hybs, 1996). In such cases, the *product* should be a fusion of psychological and external *realities* – the user should be seen as a protagonist and co-producer of narrative experience rather than a passive consumer of a product's meaning. The mental interface between the individual and the product is where the 'experience' lies (Dunne et al, 2001). As contemporary life becomes evermore programmed, the need for fiction, rich evolving narrative experiences, complexity and dialogue increases correspondingly – instead of thinking about appearance, user-friendliness or corporate identity, industrial designers could develop design proposals that challenge conventional values...new

strategies need to be developed that are both critical and optimistic, that engage with and challenge industry's technological agenda (Dunne et al, 2001).

Conclusions

Due to the everyday and oftentimes superficial nature of innovation, material culture has developed a transient, sacrificial and replaceable character. In direct consequence, our contemporary engagement with objects has become both disproportionate and volatile. Creative strategies for emotionally durable objects must be developed in reactance to this emergent trend; engaging the user on deeper and more profound levels to mediate emotionally resonant experiences that slowly infiltrate the psyche over longer periods of time; empowering the user to transcend the superficial urgencies of conventional consumerism, to forge deep emotive connections with their possessions. These new and provocative creative strategies will provide the cornerstones to positive social, economic and environmental progress, at a time of looming ecological crisis, increasing legislation and questionable levels of sustainable design progress.

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